

Parental Involvement and Attitudes Towards Basic Science and Technology on Students' Academic Performance in Eket Local Government of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined the comparative analysis between parental influence and attitudes on academic performance in Basic Science and Technology among upper Basic students in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The design was a descriptive survey research design. Population comprised all the junior secondary two (JS2) Basic science and Technology students during the 2023/2024 academic session in the 13 public secondary schools in Eket Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. A sample of 198 junior secondary two (JS2) Basic science and Technology students in 4 intact classes were selected by simple random sampling technique. A researcher developed instrument titled: "Parental involvement and Attitudes Questionnaire" was used to collect data. Reliability of the instrument was found to be 0.78 using Cronbach Alpha statistics. The data collected was analyzed using linear regression analysis to answer the research questions while the hypotheses was tested using t-test associated with regression analysis statistical tool at 0.05 level of significance. Findings of the study showed that the influence of parental involvement and attitude on Basic science and Technology on students' academic performance in Junior Secondary schools was not statistically significant. Based on the findings of the study it was recommended that parents should be encouraged to set expectations and aspirations for their children's education. Also, parents should be digitally literacy to cope with the 21st century child due to the digital divide that exists.

Keyword: Parents, Involvement, Attitudes, Students and Academic Performance

Introduction

Basic Science and Technology is taught as a core subject across all levels of the Junior Secondary Schools in Nigeria. The curriculum developers in this subject area have in mind to lay solid foundations, strong enough to support the study of the major core which include: Physic, Chemistry and Biology. Both the Universal Basic Education (UBE) Act of 2004 and the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2014) states that every learner who has completed nine years of basic education "should have numeracy, manipulative skills, communication, and lifelong skills; as well as ethical, moral, and civic values needed for laying a solid foundation for lifelong learning as the basis for scientific, and reflective thinking," according to the UBE Act of 2004, on page 16. National Policy on Education provided for nine (9) years basic and compulsory education - six (6) years of elementary education and three (3) years of junior secondary education. One of the disciplines that assist pupils in achieving their academic objectives in the first nine (9) years of school is Basic science and technology.

Kabiru and Bello (2023) describes Basic science as a Science based subject taught to students in their Junior Secondary School classes aimed at helping students to have clear and foundational knowledge about science and how it affects our daily lives. Basic science and Technology on the other hand refers to the Technology based subject taught to students in their Junior Secondary School classes aimed at helping students to have clear vision and foundational knowledge about technology. Kabiru (2017) defines technology as the application of the knowledge derived from science. Basic science education is therefore a systematic and scientific application of practical skills and theoretical knowledge of solving problems. It is the agent for sustainable national development.

Basic Science and technology education is regarded globally as the foundation of civilization and development. It is the application of scientific and technological knowledge in manufacturing and utilizing tools, techniques, resources and processes to shape the human and natural environment for individual well-being and social development. The goal of Basic Sciences education is to prepare students to grasp fundamental concepts correctly and to apply them. Additionally, it aims to foster the attitudes and abilities necessary for future scientific endeavours. According to Samuel (2017) to attain these goals, collaborative learning actions and active involvements are essential.

Good academic performance in Basic Science and Technology at the junior secondary school level is often considered requisite by parents and school counsellors for students' placement in the science class. It prepares students at the upper basic level for the study of core science subjects (Biology, Chemistry and Physics) at the senior secondary school level. For a student to be able to study single science subjects at the senior secondary level successfully, such a student has to be well grounded in Basic Science and Technology at the upper basic level. It is therefore expected that students that have achieved better grades in Basic Science and Technology should be given the opportunity to study the separate science subjects at the senior secondary school level (Agbidye, 2015). This is an important consideration as it ensures a solid science foundation at the junior school level. Apart from being used as a criterion for career in science, Basic Science and Technology teaches basic scientific concepts necessary for everyday life and survival. It provides and enhances early knowledge of nature and environment needed for environmental awareness and survival. Problem solving skills are first learnt by students in Basic Science and Technology and subsequently developed and mastered at higher studies. This is actually unexpected because early experiences in science help students to develop problem-solving skills that empower students to participate in an increasingly scientific and technological world. Students are therefore encouraged to take-up science-related subjects, study and perform well. Parents are one of the most significant factors in the development of the children. This is due to the authority and skill they have to shape and develop their children into motivated, inspired and lenient people with their explicit involvement in the process of learning activities. Contrarily, parents without involvement in their children's education process are merely considered to demotivate and demoralize their children through negligence. This, in turn, has a negative effect on their achievements. Parental variables have been largely implicated as being contributory to poor academic performance of students in junior secondary schools. Harju-Luukkainen, et al (2020) argued that learning should not be hindered or restricted in any way even if a child comes from a poor family, has an immigrant background, is raised by a single parent or has limited resources at home. It is however an undebatable fact that the home is the fulcrum around which the early years of a child revolves. The central figures are the parents. While childbearing and child-rearing cannot be divorced one from the other. The type of childrearing practiced in a family has a tremendous impact on the entire life of the child including academic life (Tobi, 2015). Parents have a lot to do to ensure that the mental, emotional and psychological balance, value orientation, aspiration and personality, as well as the academic status of their children are properly developed in life. According to Sirin (2015), parental variables are clear correlates of academic performance at the individual level (average correlation of 0.299). Students with higher family socio-economic status are found to have much higher educational achievement than those having poorer family resources, and vice versa (Okpala et al 2021; Engin-Demir, 2019; Tomul and Savasci, 2016).

It is not arguable that family-related factors, like parental involvement and attitudes play very important role on children's academic achievement in Basic Science and Technology. Parents' active involvement in their children's education has a positive and noteworthy impact on children's lives, including their development, behaviour, motivation and academic performance (Prasad 2022). According to research by Kohl *et al.*, (2020), children of parents who are involved in their academic work regularly attend school, act better, do better academically from kindergarten through high school, go farther in school and go to better schools. Becoming enthusiastically involved in children's education at home and in school, parents unknowingly send clear messages to children and demonstrate interest in children's activities. This is believed to strengthen the idea that school is important. Parents who have more than minimum level of education are expected to have favoured attitude to the child's education and to encourage and help him/her with school work (Musgrave, 2020).

Research studies have found that participation of parents in children's education was significant and positively correlated with students' academic performance (Olaniyi and Mageshni 2018, Altschul, 2021). Adolescent children whose parents participate actively in their education tend to have better attendance and academic performances in school (Hatch, 2019). Ahmed and Khalid (2021) reported that students who had been helped with or had their homework reviewed fewer times by their parents achieve significantly higher scores than those who had been helped or checked on more frequently.

A study by Rosie (2015) found that students whose parents are intently involved in their children's academic activities have better academic results than parents who are not dynamically involved in the academic activities of their children. Green *et al.* (2017) believed parents who are actively involved with their children's education are more likely to encourage the children's social, emotional, and academic growth. Barnard (2014) found that academic performance of students profoundly

depends upon the parental involvement in their academic activities to attain a higher level of quality in academic success. Since parents are the first teachers of their children, they need to take a leading role in their children's education. Parents' involvement in a child's education is a key issue ensuring students' success, growth and development in life. Students will take education more seriously, do well academically, display better behaviour in school and assume greater responsibility for his or her actions when they found their parents are actively involved.

Domitrovich and Welsh (2014) showed that parents' involvement in their children's reading activities at home had a significant influence, not only on their reading ability, language comprehension and expressive language skills, but also on their interest in reading. Particularly, Barnard (2014) showed children who worked with their parents at home on assignment achieved better grades. This goes further to demonstrate that when parents are involved in a child's schooling by assisting them with homework, communicating with teachers and attending all events at school, it helps the child to do very well in all the subjects in school. However, research by Shumow and Miller (2021) contradicted this view, revealing that parental involvement in homework and communication with the school rather has a negative impact on students' academic achievement by way of lower test scores. Additionally, Cooper *et al.* (2020) found that when parents are directly involved in children's education that will negatively affect their performance academically.

In a study by Saumendra (2020) on parental involvement and achievement of kindergarten children showed that parental involvement statistically significantly mediated the association between parental involvement and children's reading. Naite (2021) on impact of parental involvement on children's academic performance indicated that students with highly involved parents had better academic performance and higher test scores in all the subjects compared to students whose parents were not involved in their education. Prasad (2022) concluded that the greater involvement of parents results in development of positive attitudes of children toward school, classes, and enhancement of academic achievement.

Attitudes involve positive or negative feelings and reactions toward an object, place, or thing. The greater involvement of parents results in development of positive attitudes of children toward school, classes, and enhancement of academic achievement (Stevenson and Baker, 2017). Gianna and Chiara (2018) found a positive relationship between parents' attitude and students' academic performances. According to this view, in conversations with their children, some parents may assert that studying Basic Science and Technology is relevant for the future and might encourage their children to put more effort into their studies while rendering a helping hand (Harackiewicz et al, 2017). On the other hand, Prime et al., (2017) observed that many parents feel inadequate helping their children because they are not confident in their own abilities or are unaware of the content, or do not have the teaching skills needed to help their children.

It has been found however, when parents are taught how to work with their children, especially in subjects like Basic Science and Technology, they develop a better attitude towards school and the subject matter, which could influence students' attitudes toward the subject too (Eden & Mbuk, 2019). Sheldon and Epstein (2015) found a strong link between parents' and students' attitudes toward their subjects. Parents who have negative attitudes towards a subject, or who have openly acknowledged their own deficiencies tend to have children with similar attitudes. On the other hand, students who are doing well in the subjects have been traced to parents who are enthusiasts and enjoy involvement in their children's school work and assignments which increases positive attitude (Sheldon and Epstein, 2015).

Kabiru and Bello (2023) on the impact of Basic Science and Technology towards students' attitudes advocated that students in secondary schools should be exposed by the science teacher continually to challenging life situations about the benefits of science. This will help to shape their attitude positively toward science subjects, parent and school authorities should make clear to our boys and girls in schools how also in natural science fundamental questions of human life are raised and answered. Parents should make their children know that science subjects are made for both boys and girls so as to take away all forms of discrimination amongst them in the learning of science related subjects.

The background of this study is replete with indications that family-related factors play very important role on children's academic achievement in Basic science and Technology. Given the background, this study attempts to substantiate the above divergent claims by determining the truth underlying the influence or non-influence of specific parental variables; comparative analysis between parental influence and attitudes on academic performance in Basic Science and Technology among upper Basic students in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Many researches on the influence of parental variables on the academic performance of Basic Science and Technology students have been conducted in most advanced countries like Europe, America and Italy. In order to be able to correlate with these parental factors which are parental involvement and attitude as collates of academic performance of upper Basic students' in Basic science and Technology. Besides, observations have shown that not all children are bright academically which may not necessarily be as a result of poor quality of teaching and lack of basic teaching and learning facilities in the school (Tsobaza and Njoku, 2021). Hence, the need to carry out a comparative analysis of parental influence and attitudes on academic

performance in Basic science and Technology among upper Basic students with the aim of finding solution to children's poor academic performance. Also proffer solutions to help in the improvement of the quality of education of Basic science and Technology students in Eket Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The objective of the study was to determine the extent to which parental influence and attitudes affect students' academic performance in Basic Science and Technology among upper Basic students. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

1. the extent to which parental involvement influences academic performance in Basic Science and Technology among upper basic students in Eket Local Government Area.
2. the extent to which parental attitude influences academic performance in Basic Science and Technology among upper basic students in Eket Local Government Area

Research Questions

1. To what extent does parental involvement influence academic performance in Basic Science and Technology among upper basic students in Eket Local Government Area?
2. To what extent does parental attitude influence on academic performance in Basic Science and Technology among upper basic students in Eket Local Government Area?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between parental influence on academic performance in Basic Science and Technology among upper basic students in Eket Local Government Area.
2. There is no significant difference between parental attitude on academic performance in Basic Science and Technology among upper basic students' in Eket Local Government Area.

Methodology

The design adopted for the study was a descriptive survey design. The target population of this study comprised all the 1420 junior secondary two (JS2) Basic Science and Technology students in the 13 public secondary schools in Eket Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. The sample comprised of 198 students drawn from four classes from four schools in the target population. A total of four out of the thirteen public secondary schools were selected for the study by simple random sampling technique. The researcher used a self-developed questionnaire titled: Parental influence and Attitude Questionnaire as the instrument for data collection which was made up of items arranged systematically based on the research questions to collect data and information from upper basic students. The questionnaire for the students was divided into two sections: Section A elicited demographic information. While Section B was items on parental involvement and attitudes. The questionnaire was scored using the 4- points Likert scale as follows: Strongly Agree (SA) 4points, Agree (A) 3points, Disagree (D) 2points and Strongly Disagree (SD) 1 point. The instrument was vetted, necessary corrections and modifications were made after the validation by the experts before administering to respondents. In order to ascertain the reliability of the instrument, 20 questionnaires were distributed to the students not part of the sample. The data collected was tested using Cronbach Alpha technique to ascertain the reliability co-efficient and found to be 0.78. Upon getting to the sampled secondary schools, permission was obtained from the principal and the purpose of the research explained. The instrument (questionnaire) was administered personally by the researchers to the respondents. The instrument were collected back immediately to obtain high return rate. The scores of the respondents past examinations were obtained from the Vice Principals of the sampled schools. The raw scores collected (data) and the answers to the questions were analyzed using linear regression analysis. While the hypotheses were tested using t-test associated with regression analysis statistical tool at 0.05 level of significance. This is because, it is the most suitable inferential statistical tool which can determine whether significant difference exists or not.

Results

Research Question 1

To what extent does parental involvement influence academic performance in Basic Science and Technology among upper basic students in Eket Local Government Area?

Regression coefficients for influence of parental involvement on academic performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	
(Constant)	68.00	3.68		.00
Parental Influence	.074	.37	.014	.84

Fieldwork, 2024 $R = .014 R^2 = .005$

Table 1 shows unstandardized coefficient (B) of .074 for parental influence on academic performance in Basic science and Technology among upper basic students in Eket Local Government Area. This indicates that, with parental influence, there is an increase of 74% in students' performance. Also, coefficient of determination (R^2) value of .005 indicates that parental involvement has 5% influence on students' performance. While Regression coefficient (R) value of .14 (14%) indicates a low level of prediction of students' performance by parental involvement.

Research Question 2: To what extent does parental attitude influence students' academic performance in Basic Science and Technology among upper basic student in Eket Local Government Area?

Table 2: Regression coefficients for influence of parental attitude on academic performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	
(Constant)	70.15	3.65		.00
Parental Attitude	-.112	.28	-.029	.67

Fieldwork, 2023 $R = .029 R^2 = .001$

Table 2 shows unstandardized coefficient (B) of -.112 for parental attitude on academic performance in Basic science and Technology among upper basic students in Eket Local Government Area. This indicates that, with parental attitude, there is an increase of 11.2% in students' performance. Also, coefficient of determination (R^2) value of .001 indicates that parental attitude has 1% influence on students' performance. While Regression coefficient (R) value of .029 (2.9%) indicates a low level of prediction of students' performance by parental attitude.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between parental influence on academic performance in Basic science and Technology among upper basic students in Eket Local Government Area.

Table 3: Regression analysis with F value of parental influence as predictor of students' performance in Basic science and Technology

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F_{cal}	F_{crit}
Regression	4.80	1	4.80	0.04	.84
Residual	24051.96	198	121.46		
Total	24056.76	199			

Fieldwork, 2024 ($P < 0.05$)

The results in Table 3 show that the F_{cal} for parental influence on students' performance is 0.04 while its corresponding Table value, F_{crit} at df 1, 199 and $p < .05$ is .84. The F_{cal} is less than F_{crit} . This implies that there is no significant difference on academic performance in Basic science and Technology among upper basic student in Eket Local Government Area. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Research Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between parental attitude on academic performance in Basic science and Technology among upper basic students in Eket Local Government Area.

Table 4: Regression analysis with F value of parental influence as predictor of students' performance in Basic science and Technology

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F _{cal}	F _{cri}
Regression	19.73	1	19.73		0.16
Residual	24051.03	198	121.40		.69
Total	24056.76	199			

Fieldwork, 2024 (P<0.05)

The results in Table 4 showed that the F_{cal} for parental attitude on students' performance is 0.16 while its corresponding Table value, F_{crit} at df 1, 199 and p<.05 is .69. The F_{cal} is less than F_{crit}. This implies that there is no significant difference between parental attitude on academic performance in Basic science and Technology among upper basic students. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Discussion of Findings

The influence of parental involvement on Basic science and Technology students' academic performance showed that parental involvement had a 5% influence and an insignificant influence of parental involvement on Basic science and Technology students' academic performance this can be attribute to the fact that students who are undergoing free and compulsory education have to learn in spite of their parents' involvement. The 21st century child is driven by the exploration of digital technology and can find answers to questions on assignments online with the use of hand-held devices. Were as some parents are not even aware and knowledgeable of the different applications available in their technological devices.

The findings of this study is in contrast with a study by Saumendra (2020) on connections between parental marital status, parental involvement and literacy achievement of kindergarten children which showed that parental involvement statistically significantly mediated the association between parental involvement and children's reading. The findings of this study is also in contrast with that of Naite (2021) on impact of parental involvement on children's academic performance which indicated that students with highly involved parents had better academic performance and higher test scores in all the subjects compared to students whose parents were not involved in their education.

The findings from the results on the influence of parental attitude on Basic science and Technology students' academic performance had a low influence on Basic science and Technology students' academic performance. This can be attributed to the fact that different teaching strategies can be used to enhance student's performance in Basic science and Technology in spite of the parent's attitude. Finding also showed that there is no significant influence of parental attitude on Basic science and Technology students' academic performance. This is in contrast with Sheldon and Epstein (2015) that students who are doing well in the subjects were traced to parents who are enthusiasts and enjoy involvement in their children's school work and assignments which increases positive attitude.

Conclusion

In view of the findings from the study, it can be concluded that parental involvement and parental attitude had different levels of influence on Basic Science and Technology student's performance. Parental involvement influenced Basic science and Technology students' academic performance in Junior Secondary school by 5%, while parental attitude influenced by 1%. This shows that parental involvement and parental attitude are not strong determinants of students' performance.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made in view of the findings from this study that:

1. Parents should be encouraged to set expectations and aspirations for their children's education.
2. Parents should be encouraged to partner with both school and students by fostering a collaborative relationship between parents, schools and teachers, to create a support environment that promotes students success
3. Parents should be digitally literacy to cope with the 21st century child due to the digital divide that exists.

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